

Exploring the Nexus Between Teacher Communication Styles and Parental Attitudes Towards School Involvement: A Quantitative Study

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Abstract. The purpose of this study was to determine which domains of teacher communication styles significantly influence parental attitudes towards school involvement. This study used the descriptive-correlational research design. The respondents of this study were 74 parents of students enrolled in Tungkalan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division. The researcher used Tabachnick and Fidell's (2007) formula, $n = 50 + 8(m)$, in selecting the respondents. The gathered data were analyzed and interpreted using statistical tools, including the mean, Pearson r , and multiple linear regression. The results revealed that, at the level of teacher communication styles, aggressive, passive, and assertive communication styles were sometimes evident. On the other hand, the level of parental attitudes towards school involvement in terms of Parent involvement at home, parent involvement with school, and parent desires and expectations was described as oftentimes evident. Furthermore, it was found that a significant relationship exists between teacher communication styles and parental attitudes toward school involvement. Lastly, the results revealed that teacher communication styles—namely aggressive, passive, and assertive communication styles—significantly influence parental attitudes towards school involvement. Thus, it is recommended that Teachers should adopt more consistent and assertive communication strategies to engage parents and support student development effectively.

KEY WORDS

1. Teacher communication styles
2. parental attitudes
3. school involvement
4. parents
5. Davao City Division
6. Philippines

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1. Introduction

Parents, who are regarded as stakeholders in the school community, have a significant influence on their children's education. A variety of initiatives are implemented by schools to encourage increased parental involvement, with an emphasis on teacher-parent communication. Recent experimental research has demonstrated that two-way communication between teachers

and parents can result in increased parental involvement, enhanced student engagement, and academic success. Hence, healthy communication between educators and parents is of profound importance in the nurturing and education of children.

Nierva (2019) emphasized that parental participation in the Philippines is ambiguous and

inadequate, underscoring the persistent need for improved measures that effectively encourage parental engagement in both domestic and educational settings. Although Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs) exist in both public and private schools to advocate for parental involvement in academic affairs, genuine parental engagement frequently remains limited. The author contended that strengthening the collaboration between educators and parents could improve the relationship between households and educational institutions, as teachers play a crucial role in bridging this divide. This collaboration is crucial for improving student outcomes and fostering sustained parental involvement.

In Davao City, a significant research gap exists due to the scarcity of local literature examining the relationship between teacher communication styles and parental attitudes toward school involvement. Although global studies have shown the importance of communication in increasing parental involvement, there is little understanding of how these relationships play out in the local environment of Davao City. This disparity shows that local educators and politicians may be overlooking important insights that could guide more successful, locally relevant initiatives for strengthening home-school partnerships. By filling this gap, this research study could bring more insight into the relationship between teacher communication styles and parental attitudes towards school involvement.

The study aimed to address the following objectives: a) to determine the level of teacher communication styles in terms of aggressive, passive, and assertive communication styles. b.) to determine the level of parental attitudes towards school involvement in terms of parent involvement at home, parent involvement with school, and parent desires and expectations. c.) to determine if there is a significant rela-

tionship between the level of teacher communication styles and parental attitudes towards school involvement, and d.) to determine which among the domains of teacher communication styles significantly influence parental attitudes towards school involvement.

At the .05 level of significance, the following hypotheses were tested: a.) There is no significant relationship between the level of teacher communication styles and parental attitudes towards school involvement. b.) None of the domains of teacher communication styles significantly influences parental attitudes towards school involvement.

This study benefited multiple groups: teachers gained insights on communication strategies that foster stronger parental engagement, improving classroom collaboration and student outcomes; parents better understood how to interact with teachers to support their child's education; students experienced enhanced learning environments due to increased parental involvement; the Department of Education could use the findings to refine policies and training for effective teacher-parent communication; school heads received guidance to develop professional programs promoting assertive communication; and future researchers were provided a foundation to explore the broader impacts of communication styles on school dynamics, including academic performance and parental involvement.

Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual framework, which outlines the variables under investigation. It showed that the independent variable was teacher communication styles, specifically aggressive, passive, and assertive communication styles. On the other hand, the dependent variable was parental attitudes toward school involvement, encompassing parent involvement at home, parent involvement with the school, and parent desires and expectations.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

2. Methodology

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It encompasses population and sampling, instrumentation, data sources, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a descriptive-correlation quantitative design to precisely describe teacher communication styles and parental attitudes toward school involvement and to examine the strength of their relationship. The descriptive approach addressed what, where, when, and how questions without explaining why, while the correlational method assessed the extent of the relationship between these variables. As a widely used contemporary research approach, quantitative design emphasizes precise measurement, statistical analysis, and numerical data to generate insights, identify variable relationships, and develop generalizations.

2.2. Ethical Considerations—The researcher adhered to RMC’s ethical principles, ensuring informed consent, participant protection, and transparency. The study explored how teacher communication styles affect parental attitudes at Tungkalan Elementary School, benefiting all stakeholders by promoting stronger school-home ties. Informed consent was secured face-to-face, with participants fully in-

formed of their rights and the voluntary nature of participation. Confidentiality, cultural sensitivity, and safety were prioritized, with no risks posed. The researcher, qualified and guided by experts, used adequate resources and complied with the Data Privacy Act. There were no conflicts of interest, and fairness was ensured through equal treatment, clear inclusion criteria, and transparency in methods and dissemination.

2.3. Research Respondents—The respondents in this study were parents of students enrolled in Tungkalan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division, selected through universal sampling to ensure full population coverage. Using Tabachnick and Fidell’s (2007) formula for regression analysis ($n = 50 + 8m$), a minimum of 74 parents were included, based on the single independent variable: parental attitudes toward school involvement. Inclusion criteria required parents to have children currently enrolled in Grades 1–6 at the school, while those without children enrolled were excluded.

2.4. Research Instrument—This study used survey questionnaires to examine teacher

communication styles—aggressive, passive, and assertive—adapted from Bocar (2022), and parental attitudes toward school involvement—at home, with school, and in terms of desires and expectations—based on Rahman (2021). Both variables were measured using a five-point Likert scale, with clearly defined descriptive ranges from “Very Low” to “Very High.” The instruments underwent expert review for content validity and were pilot-tested in a nearby school, achieving a reliability score above .70, confirming their consistency. Feedback from experts was incorporated to refine the final version of the questionnaire, ensuring clarity, relevance, and accuracy for the study’s respondents.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The data collection process followed a structured approach to ensure accuracy and reliability. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Division Superintendent, the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, and the principals of the schools involved. The survey instruments underwent expert content

validation and were pilot-tested with 25 parents not included in the main study, confirming their reliability. Questionnaires were distributed and administered face-to-face to build rapport and clarify any questions, promoting honest responses. Completed surveys were carefully reviewed for completeness before retrieval to maintain data integrity. The data were then analyzed using SPSS, with results compared against existing literature to ensure validity and consistency.

2.6. Data Analysis—The study employed specific statistical tools to ensure accurate and meaningful analysis. The mean was used to describe the levels of teacher communication styles and parental attitudes towards school involvement. Pearson’s *r* was utilized to determine the correlation between these two variables. Lastly, multiple linear regression analysis identified which domain of teacher communication styles had the most significant influence on parental attitudes, offering deeper insights into their relationship.

3. Results

This chapter highlighted the results and discussion of the study. The presentation started from the descriptive analysis of teacher communication styles and parental attitudes towards school involvement, followed by a discussion on the correlation between the two variables. The presentation ended with the domains of teacher communication styles that significantly influence parental attitudes towards school involvement.

3.1. Level of Teacher Communication Styles—Table 1 shows the level of teacher communication styles in Tungkanan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division, which were measured by three indicators, namely: aggressive communication style, passive communication style, and assertive communication style. The mean ratings of these indicators were as follows: Aggressive Communication Style (3.31), which was moderate

and was described as sometimes evident. Passive Communication Style (3.36), which was moderate and was sometimes evident. Lastly, Assertive Communication Style (3.44), which was equivalent to high, and was described as oftentimes evident. The overall garnered mean was (3.37), which was described as moderate. This showed that the level of teacher communication styles in Tungkanan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division, namely

aggressive, passive, and assertive communication styles, was sometimes evident.

Table 1. Level of Teacher Communication Styles

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Aggressive Communication Style	3.31	Moderate
2	Passive Communication Style	3.36	Moderate
3	Assertive Communication Style	3.44	High
Overall Mean		3.37	Moderate

Legend: 1.00–1.79 = Very Low, 1.80–2.59 = Low, 2.60–3.39 = Moderate, 3.40–4.19 = High, 4.20–5.00 = Very High.

3.2. *Level of Parental Attitudes Towards School Involvement*—Table 2 shows the summary of the level of parental attitudes towards school involvement in Tungkalan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division, which was measured by three indicators, namely: parent involvement at home, parent involvement with school, and parent desires and expectations. The mean ratings of these indicators were as follows: Parent Involvement at Home (3.47), which was moderate and was described as sometimes evident. Parent Involvement

with School (3.48), which was moderate and was described as sometimes evident. Lastly, Parent Desires and Expectations (3.48), which was equivalent to high and was described as oftentimes evident. The overall garnered mean was (3.48), which was described as high. This showed that the level of parental attitudes towards school involvement in Tungkalan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division namely parent involvement at home, parent involvement with school, and parent desires and expectations was oftentimes evident.

Table 2. Summary on the Level of Parental Attitudes Towards School Involvement

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Parent Involvement at Home	3.47	Moderate
2	Parent Involvement with School	3.48	Moderate
3	Parent Desires and Expectations	3.48	High
Overall Mean		3.48	High

Legend: 1.00–1.79 = Very Low, 1.80–2.59 = Low, 2.60–3.39 = Moderate, 3.40–4.19 = High, 4.20–5.00 = Very High.

3.3. *Significant Relationship between Teacher Communication Styles and Parental Attitudes Towards School Involvement*—Table 3 displays the data on the significant relationship between teacher communication styles and parental attitudes towards school involvement. The Pearson Product-Moment Correla-

tion (Pearson r) was employed to examine the relationship between these two variables. The results revealed a computed p-value of .000, which is lower than the .05 level of significance. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between teacher communication styles and parental attitudes towards school involvement.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between Teacher Communication Styles and Parental Attitudes Towards School Involvement

Variables	r-value	Statistical Description	p-value
Decision			
Teacher Communication Styles (x) and Parental Attitudes Towards School Involvement (y)	0.87	Strong Correlation	.000***
Reject H ₀			

Note. ***p < .001. A strong positive correlation was found between teacher communication styles and parental attitudes toward school involvement.

3.4. *Domains of Teacher Communication Styles That Significantly Influence Parental Attitudes towards School Involvement*—Table 4 presents the regression analysis examining the relationship between different teacher communication styles—aggressive, passive, and assertive—and parental attitudes towards school involvement. The analysis revealed a computed r-value of 0.82 and a p-value lower than 0.000, signifying a strong positive correlation (Cohen et al., 2002) between these variables. This outcome rejects the hypothesis of no significant relationship between teacher communication styles and parental attitudes towards school involvement, confirming a high degree of correlation as observed in the study.

The results clearly demonstrate a strong and significant relationship between teacher communication styles and parental attitudes towards

school involvement. The analysis yielded an F-value of 68.84 and a p-value below 0.000, indicating a significant model fit. Furthermore, the R² value of 0.6724 implies that 67.24 percent of the variation in parental attitudes towards school involvement can be explained by the predictors, with the remaining percentage attributable to factors outside the scope of the three dimensions of teacher communication styles.

The regression coefficients reveal that all domains of teacher communication styles significantly influence parental attitudes towards school involvement. Among these domains, the assertive communication style, with an unstandardized coefficient of =0.387, exhibited the most significant influence on parental attitudes towards school involvement, as evidenced by p-values below 0.05. Consequently, this result leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 4. Domains of Teacher Communication Styles that Significantly Influence Parental Attitudes Toward School Involvement

Teacher Communication Styles	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision @ $\alpha = 0.05$
Constant	2.958	.209	—	4.868	.000	—
Aggressive Communication Style	.362	.083	.112	5.806	.001	Reject H ₀
Passive Communication Style	.321	.077	.521	3.242	.000	Reject H ₀
Assertive Communication Style	.387	.079	.405	5.324	.000	Reject H ₀

Note. Dependent Variable: Parental Attitudes toward School Involvement. R = .82, R² = .6724, F(3, N) = 68.844, p = .000.

4. Discussion

This study aimed to determine the level of teacher communication styles in terms of: (1) aggressive communication style, (2) passive communication style, and (3) assertive communication style. Further, the study also aimed to determine the level of parental attitudes towards school involvement in terms of: (1) parent involvement at home, (2) parent involvement with school, and (3) parent desires and expectations.

In addition, it also sought to have empirical evidence on the perceived relationship between teacher communication styles and parents' attitudes towards school involvement. Further, data were analyzed through scientific analysis to pinpoint which domains of teacher communication styles could significantly influence the parental attitude towards school involvement. The following are the significant findings:

On the level of teacher communication styles in terms of aggressive communication style, passive communication style, and assertive communication style, it was found to be moderate, which also means that the level of teacher communication styles of the teachers was sometimes evident. This reflects the dynamic within Bronfenbrenner's microsystem, where the teacher-parent relationship plays a vital role, and it suggests that enhancing assertive and consistent communication could better support positive mesosystem interactions that influence student outcomes.

On the other hand, the level of parental attitudes towards school involvement in terms of Parent involvement at home, parent involvement with school, and parent desires and expectations was described as high which also means that it was oftentimes evident. This supports Social Exchange Theory, showing that parents recognize the benefits of school involvement, and aligns with Bronfenbrenner's view of an engaged microsystem that fosters effective learning through active family-school collaboration.

On the results of the test of the relationship between the variables involved in the study. The

results yielded a computed correlation r-value of 0.82 with a p-value of .000, which is notably lower than the .05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming a significant relationship between teacher communication styles and parental attitudes towards school involvement. This finding is consistent with Symbolic Interactionism, as it shows that parents interpret teachers' communication behaviors in meaningful ways that influence their level of engagement, while also affirming Bronfenbrenner's emphasis on the importance of strong connections between home and school environments.

Based on the regression analysis, the results revealed that the teacher communication styles—namely aggressive communication styles, passive communication styles, and assertive communication styles significantly influence parental attitudes towards school involvement by registering a p-value of .000, which is less than .05 in the level of significance. This suggests that teacher communication directly shapes parental engagement decisions, in line with Social Exchange Theory's view on cost-benefit evaluation, and reinforces the idea from Symbolic Interactionism that communication styles carry symbolic meaning that impacts how parents choose to participate in their children's education.

Based on the findings and conclusions, several recommendations were proposed: Teachers should consistently use assertive and respectful communication to foster strong home-school partnerships and avoid overly aggressive or passive styles. Parents are encouraged to stay actively involved by maintaining open communication with teachers and participating in school activities. Students can benefit by modeling respectful, assertive communication learned from parents and teachers. The Department of Education should offer professional development focused on enhancing teachers' communication skills. School heads should support this

by organizing workshops and promoting clear, empathetic communication policies. Future researchers are advised to examine the long-term impact of teacher communication styles on parental involvement and explore effective strategies across diverse cultural and socioeconomic settings.

5. References

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